

Crown Ether Complexation of Cationic Lanthanide(III) Chloride Species : Crystal and Molecular Structures of $[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})]\text{-}[\text{SbCl}_6]\cdot 5\text{THF}$ (1), and $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})][\text{SbCl}_6]_3$ (2)

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Halide abstraction from a lanthanide(III) chloride using antimony(V) chloride as abstractor provides cationic metal species which can be stabilized *in situ* by crown ether complexation. The syntheses and structures of two such antimonate salts are presented. For $[\text{DyCl}_2(12\text{-crown-4})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2][\text{SbCl}_6]\cdot 5\text{THF}$ (1) the structure comprises independent $[\text{DyCl}_2(12\text{-crown-4})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ cations and SbCl_6^- anions with lattice solvent (tetrahydrofuran) molecules. The cation structure has an approximate two-fold axis and the eight-coordinate metal environment can be considered as distorted square-antiprismatic. The Dy–O(crown) bond distances are equivalent 2.515(11) Å, the Dy–Cl bond distances are 2.631(5), 2.646(4) Å and the Dy–O(H₂O) bond distances are 2.364(10), 2.373(11) Å. In the case of $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})][\text{SbCl}_6]_3$ (2) the independent nine-coordinate $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})]^{3+}$ cations show crystallographic C₂ symmetry with each metal centre being bonded to all four oxygen atoms of the two rings and to a nitrogen atom of a coordinated acetonitrile molecule. The Er–O(crown) bond lengths lie in the range 2.443(9)–2.503(9) Å, mean 2.463(9) Å and the Er–N bond length is 2.56(2) Å. The planes of the two oxa-crown rings intersect at an angle of 73.0(1)°.

Perhaps the most intriguing aspect of lanthanide(III) halide-macrocyclic polyether complexation is the strikingly diverse structural chemistry of the resulting metal compounds. This is reflected not only in the variations observed in the metal coordination geometries but also with respect to the metal-ligand binding. For the latter, two distinct types have been identified: *second sphere coordination* where the metal is only loosely associated with the crown ether via $\text{O}_{\text{crown}} \cdots \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdots \text{M}$ hydrogen bonding interactions and *encapsulation* which features the metal trapped in the crown cavity and directly bound through $\text{M} \cdots \text{O}_{\text{crown}}$ interactions. The main factors which can affect the resulting metal geometries/structures of such complexes include the size of the macrocyclic ring cavity, the size of the lanthanide ion, the choice of solvent and, in some cases, the conditions of recrystallization¹.

The focus of this work lies with the reactions of dysprosium(III) chloride and erbium(III) chloride with the oxa-crown ligand 12-crown-4 in the presence of SbCl_5 as halide abstractor. A search of the Cambridge Crystallographic Database reveals the following Ln(III)–(12-crown-4) structures²:

As an extension to this list we report herein the synthesis and X-ray structural characterization of $[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})][\text{SbCl}_6]\cdot 5\text{THF}$ (1), and $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})][\text{SbCl}_6]_3$ (2).

Results and Discussion

$[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})][\text{SbCl}_6]\cdot 5\text{THF}$ (1): It was obtained from the reaction system $\text{DyCl}_3(\text{THF})_{3.5}/12\text{-crown-4}/\text{SbCl}_5/\text{MeCN}$ as colorless plate crystals following recrystallization of the initial product from THF. An X-ray structure determination revealed discrete $[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})]^+$ cations, SbCl_6^- anions and 5 solvent (THF) molecules trapped in the lattice. The SbCl_6^- anions arouse little interest; they show octahedral geometry with Sb–Cl bond distances in the range 2.26(2) to 2.51(2) Å and *cis* Cl–Sb–Cl angles between 84.8(6) and 96.7(7)°.

Fig. 1. The structure of the $[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})]^+$ cation in 1. Ellipsoids are shown at 30% probability. Hydrogen atoms are included with small arbitrary radii.

The structure of the $[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})]^+$ cation is shown in Fig. 1 together with the atom labelling used. Salient bond lengths and angles are listed in Table 1. The central dysprosium atom is eight-coordinate, being bound to the four oxygen atoms of the oxa-crown, two chlorine atoms and two water molecules. The water molecules most likely originate from a 'wet' sample of the 12-crown-4 ligand and/or impurities in the solvents during recrystallization.

The structure has an approximate two-fold axis and the metal environment can be considered to be a distorted square-antiprism with the crown forming one face and the two chlorine atoms and two water molecules constituting the other. The crown face involving the four oxygen atoms from the ring is planar with a maximum deviation of 0.005 Å. The face of chlorines and water molecules is much more distorted, primarily because of the difference in size of the chlorine and oxygen atoms, with a maximum deviation of 0.239 Å. The bond lengths to the water molecules are 2.364(10), 2.373(11) Å, to the chlorine atoms are 2.631(5) and 2.646(4) Å and to the oxygen atoms of the crown are 2.514(11), 2.515(12) and 2.515(12) and 2.515(11) Å.

TABLE 1—DIMENSIONS IN THE METAL COORDINATION SPHERES IN COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2

In compd. 1 :	
Dy(1)-O(200)	2.364(10)
Dy(1)-O(100)	2.373(11)
Dy(1)-O(7)	2.514(11)
Dy(1)-O(4)	2.515(11)
Dy(1)-O(1)	2.515(12)
Dy(1)-O(10)	2.515(11)
Dy(1)-Cl(1)	2.631(5)
Dy(1)-Cl(2)	2.646(4)
O(200)-Dy(1)-O(100)	136.2(5)
O(200)-Dy(1)-O(7)	74.1(4)
O(100)-Dy(1)-O(7)	138.3(4)
O(200)-Dy(1)-O(4)	75.3(4)
O(100)-Dy(1)-O(4)	138.2(4)
O(7)-Dy(1)-O(4)	64.7(4)
O(200)-Dy(1)-O(1)	138.9(4)
O(100)-Dy(1)-O(1)	74.8(4)
O(7)-Dy(1)-O(1)	99.5(4)
O(4)-Dy(1)-O(1)	65.8(4)
O(200)-Dy(1)-O(10)	137.2(4)
O(100)-Dy(1)-O(10)	75.2(4)
O(7)-Dy(1)-O(10)	65.6(3)
O(4)-Dy(1)-O(10)	98.9(4)
O(1)-Dy(1)-O(10)	64.6(4)
O(200)-Dy(1)-Cl(1)	79.4(3)
O(100)-Dy(1)-Cl(1)	78.6(3)
O(7)-Dy(1)-Cl(1)	142.8(3)
O(4)-Dy(1)-Cl(1)	83.8(3)
O(1)-Dy(1)-Cl(1)	83.7(3)
O(10)-Dy(1)-Cl(1)	143.0(3)
O(200)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	78.8(3)

Table-1 (contd.)

O(100)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	78.9(3)
O(7)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	82.0(3)
O(4)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	142.2(3)
O(1)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	141.5(3)
O(10)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	81.9(3)
Cl(1)-Dy(1)-Cl(2)	118.0(2)
In compd. 2 :	
Er(1)-O(1)	2.443(9)
Er(1)-O(10)	2.447(9)
Er(1)-O(7)	2.458(9)
Er(1)-O(4)	2.503(9)
Er(1)-N(100)	2.56(2)
O(1)-Er(1)-O(1) ^{#1}	157.8(6)
O(1)-Er(1)-O(10)	132.8(4)
O(1) ^{#1} -Er(1)-O(10)	67.7(4)
O(10)-Er(1)-O(10) ^{#1}	77.7(5)
O(1)-Er(1)-O(7)	73.9(4)
O(1) ^{#1} -Er(1)-O(7)	116.1(4)
O(10)-Er(1)-O(7)	66.6(4)
O(10) ^{#1} -Er(1)-O(7)	74.9(3)
O(7)-Er(1)-O(7) ^{#1}	130.0(6)
O(1)-Er(1)-O(4)	66.2(4)
O(1) ^{#1} -Er(1)-O(4)	104.9(4)
O(10)-Er(1)-O(4)	138.7(3)
O(10) ^{#1} -Er(1)-O(4)	80.5(4)
O(7)-Er(1)-O(4)	138.8(3)
O(7) ^{#1} -Er(1)-O(4)	64.3(3)
O(4)-Er(1)-O(4) ^{#1}	135.8(5)
O(1)-Er(1)-N(100)	76.0(8)
O(1) ^{#1} -Er(1)-N(100)	81.8(8)
O(10)-Er(1)-N(100)	141.6(9)
O(10) ^{#1} -Er(1)-N(100)	140.2(9)
O(7)-Er(1)-N(100)	110.6(8)
O(7) ^{#1} -Er(1)-N(100)	119.4(8)
O(4)-Er(1)-N(100)	70.2(9)
O(4) ^{#1} -Er(1)-N(100)	65.7(9)

From comparisons with $[\text{DyCl}(\text{18-crown-6})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, (nine-coordinate) Dy-Cl 2.654(2) Å³, $[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{THF})_5]^+$, (seven-coordinate) Dy-Cl 2.581(6)⁴ and 2.624(5) Å⁵, $\text{DyCl}_3(\text{HMPA})_3$ (six-coordinate) Dy-Cl 2.626(4), 2.637(2), 2.634(1) *mean* 2.632(4) Å⁶, $\text{DyCl}_3(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4)(\text{18-crown-6})$, (seven-coordinate) where $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4 = \text{triethylene glycol}$, Dy-Cl 2.621(2), 2.607(2) Å⁷ and $[\text{Dy}_2(\text{dibenzo-18-crown-6})_2\text{Cl}_4]^{2+}[\text{Dy}_2\text{Cl}_8(\text{MeCN})_2]^{2-}$ whose dimensions are cation (nine-coordinate) Dy-Cl 2.594(2) Å and anion (six-coordinate) Dy-Cl 2.558(3), 2.595(2), 2.567(3) Å⁸ there is clearly precious little variation in Dy-Cl bond distance(s) between charged/neutral Dy^{III} species over the coordination range (6–9).

$[\text{Er}(\text{12-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})][\text{SbCl}_6]_3$ (2) : As demonstrated recently in the case of scandium(III) chloride, SbCl_5 is capable of total removal of chlorine atoms from the parent metal halide, i.e. formation of the 'sandwich' ion $[\text{Sc}(\text{12-crown-4})_2]^{3+}$ from the $\text{ScCl}_3(\text{THF})_3/\text{12-crown-4}/\text{SbCl}_5$ sys-

tem⁹. In the same vein, treatment of $\text{ErCl}_3(\text{THF})_{3.5}$ with a large excess of SbCl_5 (~10-fold) in acetonitrile solution in the presence of 12-crown-4 provides the title compound as colourless cubic crystals following recrystallization of the initial bulk product from methanol/dichloromethane (1 : 1). X-Ray structural characterization of **2** shows independent $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})]^{3+}$ cations and SbCl_6^- anions. Again the SbCl_6^- anions are unremarkable and show octahedral geometry with dimensions similar to those observed in **1**. The structure of the $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})]^{3+}$ cation which has crystallographic C_2 symmetry

Fig. 2. The structure of the $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})_2(\text{MeCN})]^{3+}$ cation in **2**. Ellipsoids are shown at 30% probability. Hydrogen atoms are excluded for clarity.

is shown in Fig. 2 with the atom notation used. Selected bond lengths and angles are listed in Table 1. The central metal ion is nine-coordinate and is sandwiched between the two oxa-crown ligands with an additional coordinated solvent (acetonitrile) molecule squeezed in amidships. The four oxygen atoms are almost coplanar with deviations O(1) 0.13, O(4) -0.08, O(7) -0.13, O(10) 0.08 Å. The metal atom is -0.55 Å from this plane. The two rings intersect at an angle of 73.0(1)°, presumably the relatively large size of Er^{3+} can accommodate an 'extra' coordinated solvent (MeCN) molecule which acts as a 'wedge' and is directly responsible for the tilting of the two rings. The bond lengths to the oxygen atoms are 2.443(9), 2.447(9), 2.458(9) and 2.503(9) Å and to the nitrogen atom 2.56(2) Å. As a direct comparison of ligand attachment the metal-O(crown) bond distances in related $\text{Er}^{\text{III}}/12\text{-crown-4}$ compounds range from $[\text{Er}(12\text{-crown-4})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{3+}$ (nine-coor-

dinate) 2.488(7) to 2.528(7) *mean* 2.502(7) Å and $[\text{ErCl}_2(12\text{-crown-4})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (eight-coordinate) 2.429(5) to 2.457(5) *mean* 2.443(5) Å².

Experimental

Manipulations were carried out using a Schlenk high vacuum system in conjunction with a standard dinitrogen filled glove-box. All solvents were pre-dried over CaH_2 and subsequently P_4O_{10} , and then freshly distilled under a dinitrogen atmosphere prior to use. The reagents $\text{DyCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ErCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, SbCl_5 , and 12-crown-4 were used as supplied (Aldrich). The dehydrating agent SOCl_2 was stored over molecular sieves (4A, beads 4-8 mesh; Aldrich) and then freshly distilled prior to use.

Ir spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 580B spectrometer with samples as nujol mulls placed between CsI discs. Elemental analyses were carried out using a Leeman Labs Inc., PS1000 sequential inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometer and a CE440 elemental (C, H, N) analyser.

$\text{DyCl}_3(\text{THF})_{3.5}$: Freshly distilled SOCl_2 (20.0 cm³, 274.19 mmol) was added dropwise to a cooled (0°), stirred solution of $\text{DyCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4.32 g, 11.46 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (70 cm³), and the mixture was heated at reflux for 10 h. Removal of solvents *in vacuo* from the resulting clear solution provided a grey solid which was washed with ether (3 × 25 cm³) and hexane (2 × 25 cm³) and then pumped *in vacuo* for 4 h. Recrystallization from tetrahydrofuran gave the title compound as colourless cubic crystals (5.12 g, 85.7%) (Found: C, 31.38; H, 5.13; Cl, 20.01; Dy, 30.92. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_7\text{Dy}_2\text{Cl}_6$ calcd. for: C, 32.26; H, 5.42; Cl, 20.41; Dy, 31.18%; $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ (nujol) 1306(m), 1170(s), 1075(m), 1010(s) $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COC})$, 919(m), 858(s) $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COC})$, 771(w), 722(s), 668(w), 565(vw), 497(vw)(ligand), 276(vs) br, 240(s) br $\nu(\text{DyCl})$.

$\text{ErCl}_3(\text{THF})_{3.5}$: Reagents SOCl_2 (20.0 cm³, 274.19 mmol), $\text{ErCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3.60 g, 9.43 mmol) were used. Following the same procedure as above, it was obtained as a pale pink semicrystalline solid (4.32 g, 87.1%) (Found: C, 31.62; H, 5.24; Cl, 21.01; Er, 31.56. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_7\text{Er}_2\text{Cl}_6$ calcd. for: C, 31.97; H, 5.37; Cl, 20.22; Er, 31.80%; $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ (nujol) 1345(m), 1298(m), 1174(m), 1120(m), 1019(s) $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COC})$, 921(m), 852(s) $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COC})$, 723(w), 675(w) (ligand), 262(vs) br $\nu(\text{ErCl})$.

$[\text{DyCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(12\text{-crown-4})][\text{SbCl}_6] \cdot 5\text{THF}$ (**1**): Direct addition of a solution of SbCl_5 (0.29 g, 0.959 mmol) in acetonitrile (10 cm³) to a stirred and chilled (0°) solution of $\text{DyCl}_3(\text{THF})_{3.5}$ (0.50 g, 0.959 mmol) in acetonitrile (30 cm³) yielded a clear brown solution. Following dropwise addition of 12-crown-4 (0.17 g, 0.965 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 cm³), the resulting mixture was maintained at 50° for 12 h. Removal of the solvent *in vacuo* provided a light grey solid which was washed with toluene (2 × 25 cm³) and hexane (2 × 20 cm³) and pumped to dryness. Recrystallization from acetonitrile provided the title compound as colourless plate crystals (0.78 g, 73.6%), m.p. >250°d

TABLE 2—CRYSTAL DATA AND STRUCTURE REFINEMENT FOR COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2

	1	2
Identification code	[DyCl ₂ (12-crown-4)(H ₂ O) ₂] [SbCl ₆] 5THF	[Er(12-crown-4) ₂ (MeCN)] [SbCl ₆] ₃
Empirical formula	C ₂₈ H ₆₀ Cl ₈ DyO ₁₁ Sb	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ Cl ₁₈ ErNO ₈ Sb ₃
Formula weight	1140.61	1564.08
Temperature (K)	293(2)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	monoclinic	orthorhombic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c	Pbcn
Unit cell dimensions		
(a/Å)	16.688(12)	16.666(11)
(b/Å)	14.034(14)	18.600(12)
(c/Å)	24.49(2)	16.015(12)
(β/deg)	108.27(1)	(90)
Volume (Å ³)	5445(8)	4965(6)
Z	4	8
Density (calculated) Mg/m ⁻³	1.391	2.093
Absorption coefficient mm ⁻¹	2.289	4.292
F(000)	2276	2964
Crystal size (mm)	0.20 × 0.25 × 0.25	0.25 × 0.20 × 0.10
Theta range for data collection	1.94–25.31	1.64–24.81
Index ranges	–19 < = h < = 19 0 < = k < = 15 –29 < = l < = 28	0 < = h < = 19 –21 < = k < = 21 –16 < = l < = 18
Reflections collected	16586	10502
Independent reflections (Rint)	9135(0.0646)	3547(0.0818)
Weighting Scheme (a,b)	0.113, 109.66	0.218, 0.000
Data/restraints/parameters	9135/10/319	3547/0/230
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.074	1.008
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R ₁ 0.1098 wR ₂ 0.2721	0.0940 0.2349
R indices (all data)	R ₁ 0.1522 wR ₂ 0.3013	0.1195 0.2731
Largest diff. peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	1.951 –2.058	2.135 –2.836

* Weighting scheme $w = 1/(\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (aP)^2 + bP)$, where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.

(Found : C, 28.90; H, 5.14; Cl, 24.93. C₂₈H₆₀Cl₈O₁₁SbDy calcd. for : C, 29.48; H, 5.30; Cl, 24.87%); $\bar{\nu}_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ (nujol) 3344(m) br v(OH), 1298(m), 1171(w), 1138(m), 1064(s), 1029(s), 1009(s), 932(s), 863(s), 796(w), 671(m), 547(m) ligand, 345(s) br v(SbCl), 250(s) br v(DyCl).

[Er(12-crown-4)₂(MeCN)][SbCl₆]₃ (2) : Addition of a solution of SbCl₅ (1.48 g, 4.95 mmol) in acetonitrile (30 cm³) to a cooled (0°) and stirred solution of ErCl₃(THF)_{3.5} (0.31 g, 0.59 mmol) in acetonitrile (30 cm³) and subsequent stirring at room temperature for 6 h provided a clear reddish brown solution. Subsequent addition of a solution of 12-crown-4 (0.20 g, 1.14 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 cm³) gave a faint red solution which was stirred and maintained at 50° for 12 h. Removal of solvent *in vacuo* afforded an off-white powder which was washed with toluene (2 × 20 cm³) and hexane (2 × 20 cm³) and then pumped to dryness *in vacuo*. Recrystallization from

methanol/dichloromethane (1 : 1) gave the title compound as small colorless cubic crystals (0.72 g, 77.6%) (Found : C, 13.88; H, 2.42; N, 0.87; Cl, 40.26. C₁₈H₃₅NCl₁₈O₈Sb₃Er calcd. for : C, 13.82; H, 2.26; N, 0.90; Cl, 40.80%); $\bar{\nu}_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ (nujol) 2299(m), 2272(m) v(CN), 1360(m), 1091(m), 1067(s), 1050(s), 1022(s), 932(s), 859(s) ligand, 345(vs) br v(SbCl).

X-Ray crystallography : Crystal data are given in Table 2, together with refinement details. Data for both the crystals were collected with MoK α radiation using the MAR Research Image Plate System. The crystals were positioned at 75 mm from the Image Plate. 95 frames were measured at 2° intervals with a counting time of 2 min. Data analysis was carried out with the XDS program¹⁰. The two structures were solved using direct methods with the Shelx86 program¹¹. Normally the non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters but with some excep-

tions. In compound **1**, the SbCl_6^- anion was disordered and two sets of chlorine octahedra were refined isotropically with occupancies of x and $1-x$; x refined to 0.56(2). There were six solvent (THF) molecules (two of these were given 50% occupancy) which were refined isotropically. For compound **2** the acetonitrile group bonded to the metal was disordered around the two-fold axis and was refined isotropically with 50% occupancy with the atoms slightly displaced from the axis. In both the structures, the hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were included in geometric positions, methyl groups were refined as rigid groups. The hydrogen atoms bonded to the water molecules attached to the metal in compound **1** could not be located and were not included. An empirical absorption correction was applied to both the structures¹². The structures were then refined on F^2 using Shelxl¹³. All calculations were carried out on a Silicon Graphics R4000 Workstation at the University of Reading.

Supplementary materials available : Crystal data with refinement details, atomic coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters, bond lengths and bond angles for both molecules, anisotropic displacement parameters, hydrogen atom coordinates, and FO-FC listings will be available from the authors.

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